

1 **Modelling the enantioresolution capability of cellulose tris(3,5-**
2 **dichlorophenylcarbamate) stationary phase in reversed phase**
3 **conditions for neutral and basic chiral compounds**

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11 **ABSTRACT**

12 To the best of our knowledge, the prediction of the enantioresolution ability of
13 polysaccharides-based stationary phases in liquid chromatography for structurally
14 unrelated compounds has not been previously reported. In this study, structural
15 information of neutral and basic compounds is used to model their enantioresolution
16 levels obtained from an immobilised cellulose tris(3,5-dichlorophenylcarbamate)
17 stationary phase in reversed phase conditions. Thirty-four structurally unrelated chiral
18 drugs and pesticides, from seven families, are studied. Categorical enantioresolution
19 levels (*RsC*, 0 = no baseline enantioresolution and 1 = baseline enantioresolution) are
20 established from the experimental enantioresolution values obtained at a fixed
21 experimental conditions. From 58 initial structural variables, three topological parameters
22 (two of them connected to the chiral carbon), and six molecular descriptors (one of them
23 also related with the chiral carbon), are selected after a discriminant partial least squares
24 refinement process. The molar total charge of the molecule at the working pH is the most
25 important variable. The relationships between *RsC* and the most important structural
26 variables and the drug/pesticide family are evaluated. An explicit model is proposed to
27 anticipate the *RsC* levels, which provides 100% of correct anticipations. A criterion is
28 introduced to alert about the compounds that should not be anticipated.

29 **Keywords:**

30 Cellulose tris(3,5-dichlorophenylcarbamate) stationary phase

31 Reversed phase liquid chromatography

32 Enantioseparations

33 Enantioresolution modelling

34 Discriminant partial least squares

35

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41 **1. Introduction**

42 Chiral molecules play an important role in life and medicinal sciences as well as
43 in other fields such as food and environmental chemistry. Consequently, analytical
44 techniques capable of differentiating between enantiomers are of great importance.
45 Chromatographic and capillary electromigration techniques are the most employed
46 analytical separation techniques [1-5].

47 Due to its simplicity and accuracy, high-performance liquid chromatography
48 (HPLC) with chiral stationary phases (CSPs) is one of the most widely used analytical
49 technique for enantiomeric separations. The basis of analytical enantioseparations, in the
50 so-called direct approach, is the formation of transient diastereomeric complexes between
51 the compound and the chiral selector coated or immobilized onto the stationary phase.
52 Different CSPs containing macromolecular selectors (i.e. proteins, polysaccharide
53 derivatives, polymers, etc.), macrocyclic selectors (i.e. cyclodextrins, macrocyclic
54 antibiotics, etc.) and low-molecular mass selectors (i.e. ligand exchange, chiral ion
55 exchange, etc.) have been developed [1]. More than a hundred CSPs are offered
56 commercially and about 20–30 CSPs are the most frequently employed [4].

57 In spite of the wide number of analytical applications of CSPs in HPLC, the
58 fundamental mechanisms responsible for the observed chiral separations are not fully
59 understood. In fact, today, the evaluation of the ability of a chiral column in HPLC for
60 the enantioseparation of compounds is an expensive and time-consuming trial-and-error
61 strategy. Thus, the prediction of whether a CPS is able to perform a chiral separation or
62 not is of great benefit. Relatively few articles in the literature address this important issue
63 in chiral HPLC method development.

64 Polysaccharide based stationary phases represent by far the most widely used
65 CSPs in HPLC due to their broad applicability for a large structural diversity of
66 compounds. These CSPs, which can be coated or immobilised onto the stationary support,
67 are cellulose- and amylose-based. These linear helical polymers are composed of glucose
68 units with β (1 \rightarrow 4) (cellulose) or α (1 \rightarrow 4) (amylose) linkages. The hydroxyl groups of
69 the glucose molecules are derivatised with benzoate or phenylcarbamate moieties, which
70 accept methyl groups and/or chlorine substituents in various positions on the aromatic
71 ring, yielding a large variety of derivatives with different selectivities and applications
72 [2-5]. Even, differences in enantioseparations between the CPSs containing the same
73 chiral selector either coated or covalently immobilised onto the surface of silica have been
74 achieved [4].

75 Selector-selectand complexes are thought to be mediated via hydrogen bonds to
76 the CO or NH groups of the carbamate moieties, as well as by π - π interactions between
77 the phenyl rings, Van der Waals forces and steric factors [3, 5-8]. Recently, halogen
78 bonding has been also described to contribute to selector-selectand complexation [9].

79 In chiral HPLC using polysaccharides-based stationary phases, normal, polar or
80 reversed mobile phase conditions can be used. The mobile phase composition modulates
81 the recognition process. Different chromatographic behaviours are obtained depending
82 on the nature and composition of the mobile phase, due to changes produced in the intra-
83 molecular hydrogen bonds of the polysaccharide structure. Thus, reversal of the elution
84 order enantiomers depending on the composition of the mobile phase can be observed
85 [4].

86 In order to elucidate the chiral recognition mechanism of polysaccharide chiral
87 selectors, analytical separation techniques in combination with spectroscopic techniques

88 such as NMR spectroscopy, Fourier transform and attenuated total reflectance IR
89 spectroscopy, vibrational circular dichroism techniques as well as X-ray crystallography
90 have been used [1-8]. Molecular modelling has also become a practical tool for evaluating
91 the interactions between polysaccharide-based selectors and chiral compounds [2, 10].

92 Chemometric and chemoinformatic data mining methods might be helpful to
93 extract valuable information on molecular recognition [11-12]. Among these, quantitative
94 structure–property relationships (QSPRs) are a powerful option. Different QSPR studies
95 have been reported for modelling data in enantioselective chromatography using
96 polysaccharides-based stationary phases, some of them are presented/reviewed in the
97 paper by Del Rio [11]. In these QSPR models, enantioresolution-related information
98 (retention or selectivity values) is correlated with different molecular properties of
99 compounds through linear free energy relationships (LFERs) studies [13-16], linear
100 solvation energy relationships (LSERs) [17], and 3D-QSPR properties employing
101 comparative molecular field analysis (CoMFA) [18]. Multiple linear regression (MLR)
102 [15-17], artificial neural networks [18], and genetic algorithm [16, 18] are used as
103 chemometric techniques.

104 These studies are usually carried out for structurally related compounds using
105 amylose and cellulose-based CSPs -amylose tris(3,5-dimethylphenylcarbamate) [13, 15],
106 cellulose tris(3,5-dimethylphenylcarbamate) [18] and immobilised amylose tris(5-chloro-
107 2-methylphenylcarbamate) [16]-, and normal and polar mobile phases. In these studies,
108 information about the functional groups responsible for enantioresolution is usually
109 obtained. It should be noted that resolution values between enantiomers have never been
110 used as response variable, although it is the most practical term that describes how well
111 two peaks are resolved.

112 In previous papers [19-20], the enantioresolution level (R_sC -level) of structurally
113 unrelated basic drugs and pesticides, using sulfated β - and γ -cyclodextrins as chiral
114 selectors in electrokinetic chromatography (EKC), was modelled as a function of
115 structural parameters. For sulfated β -cyclodextrin, few structural descriptors, easy to
116 obtain from a free on-line database, were selected [19]. In the case of sulfated γ -
117 cyclodextrin, few topological parameters, mainly connected to the chiral carbon (so called
118 C^* -parameters) were used [20].

119 In this work, 58 structural predictor variables of 34 structurally unrelated
120 compounds (basic drugs and pesticides), previously assayed in the above-mentioned
121 papers, are tested to model a categorical enantioresolution R_sC , as response variable. The
122 main aim is to define a protocol able to anticipate the enantioresolution ($R_sC = 1$) or not
123 ($R_sC = 0$) of new compounds based on this model. The R_sC levels are assigned from
124 experimental enantioresolution (R_s) values obtained using an immobilised cellulose
125 tris(3,5-dichlorophenylcarbamate) CSP and hydro-organic mobile phases. To the best of
126 our knowledge, this is the first report that models the enantioresolution of structurally
127 unrelated compounds separated using immobilised cellulose tris(3,5-
128 dichlorophenylcarbamate) CSP and hydro-organic mobile phases. On the other hand, the
129 importance of the predictive power (Pp) statistic to assess a discriminant partial least
130 squares for one response categorical variable (DPLS1) refinement is discussed. In
131 addition, the relationships between R_sC and the most important structural variables and
132 the drug/pesticide family are evaluated.

133

134 **2. Materials and methods**

135 *2.1. Instrumentation*

136 An Agilent Technologies 1100 chromatograph (Palo Alto, CA, USA) with a
137 binary pump, an UV–visible diode array detector, a column thermostat and an
138 autosampler was used. Data acquisition and processing were performed by means of the
139 LC/MSD ChemStation software (B.04.02 SP1 [208], ©Agilent Technologies 2001-
140 2010).

141 Prior to injection into the chromatographic system, analytes solutions were filtered
142 through disposable 0.22 µm polyethersulphone syringe filters (Frisenette, Knebel,
143 Denmark). Mobile phase solutions were vacuum-filtered through 0.22 µm Nylon
144 membranes (Micron Separations, Westboro, MA, USA) and were degassed in an
145 Elmasonic S60 ultrasonic bath (Elma, Singen, Germany) prior to use. A Crison MicropH
146 2000 pHmeter (Crison Instruments, Barcelona, Spain) was employed to adjust the pH of
147 the buffer solutions.

148

149 *2.2. Chemicals and solutions*

150 All reagents were of analytical grade. Ammonium acetate, sodium dihydrogen
151 phosphate monohydrate, sodium hydroxide, acetonitrile and methanol (®Multisolvent,
152 HPLC grade) were from Scharlau, S.L. (Barcelona, Spain). Diethylamine was from Acros
153 Organics (Geel, Belgium). 10 mM ammonium acetate buffer solution was prepared by
154 dissolving the appropriate amount of ammonium acetate in water and adjusting the pH to
155 8.0 with 2.5 M sodium hydroxide. Ultra Clear TWF UV deionised water (SG Water,
156 Barsbüttel, Germany) was used to prepare solutions.

157 Brompheniramine maleate, carbinoxamine maleate, chlorpheniramine maleate,
158 clemastine fumarate, doxylamine succinate, ethopropazine hydrochloride, hydroxyzine
159 hydrochloride, methadone hydrochloride, methotrimeprazine maleate, nomifensine
160 maleate, orphenadrine hydrochloride, pindolol, terfenadine, trimeprazine hemi(+)-tartrate
161 and verapamil hydrochloride were from Sigma (St. Louis, MO, USA). Citalopram
162 hydrobromide was from Tokyo Chemical Industry (Tokyo, Japan). Promethazine
163 hydrochloride and salbutamol sulfate were from Guinama (Valencia, Spain). All the rest
164 of drugs tested were kindly donated by several pharmaceutical laboratories: acebutolol
165 hydrochloride by Italfarmaco (Madrid, Spain); atenolol by Zeneca Farma (Madrid,
166 Spain); fluoxetine hydrochloride by Alter (Madrid, Spain); mepivacaine hydrochloride
167 and prilocaine hydrochloride by Laboratorios Inibsa (Barcelona, Spain); metoprolol
168 tartrate by Ciba Geigy (Barcelona, Spain); propanocaine by Laboratorio Seid (Barcelona,
169 Spain); propranolol hydrochloride by ICI Farma (Madrid, Spain); timolol maleate by
170 Merck Sharp & Dohme (Madrid, Spain); and viloxazine hydrochloride by Astra Zeneca
171 (Cheshire, UK). All racemic pesticides (benalaxyl, hexaconazole, imazalil, myclobutanil,
172 metalaxyl and penconazole) were from Dr. Ehrenstofer (Augsburg, Germany).

173 Stock standard solutions of compounds used in this study were prepared by
174 dissolving 10 mg of the racemic mixture in 10 mL of methanol. Working solutions were
175 prepared by dilution of the stock standard solutions using the mobile phase solution. The
176 solutions were stored under refrigeration at 5°C.

177

178 2.3. Methodology for the chiral separation of compounds

179 The experimental enantioresolution (R_s) values of the compounds listed in Table
180 1 were obtained using an immobilised cellulose tris(3,5-dichlorophenylcarbamate)
181 column (Chiralart Cellulose-SC; 3 μm , 150 \times 4.6 mm i.d.; YMC Separation Technology
182 Co., Ltd.; Tokyo, Japan). A ternary mixture consisting of ammonium acetate buffer (10
183 mM, pH 8) / acetonitrile / diethylamine (60/40/0.1, v/v/v) was used as mobile phase. The
184 mobile phase flow rate was 1.0 mL min^{-1} and the injection volume was 2 μL . The
185 detection was performed in the UV at 220 nm for all compounds, except for
186 ethopropazine, methotrimeprazine, promethazine and trimeprazine whose detection was
187 performed at 254 nm. The column was thermostatted at 25 $^\circ\text{C}$.

188

189 2.4. Software and calculations

190 Most of the structural variables used in this study were taken from the online
191 ChemSpider chemical structure database [21] and were previously assayed in a study to
192 anticipate the experimental enantioresolution of chiral compounds in electrokinetic
193 chromatography using two sulfated cyclodextrins as chiral selectors [19, 20]. The first
194 seven variables (x_1 to x_7) correspond to the C^* -parameters. These parameters are
195 calculated as the count of atoms/groups bonded to the chiral carbon (C^*), for instance C^*X
196 (C^* -heteroatoms) and C^*hA (C^* -aromatic heterocycles) [20]. Variables x_8 to x_{25}
197 correspond to molecular descriptors predicted by ACD/Labs and ChemAxon
198 calculations: minimal z length (z_{min}), molecular surface area (MSA), orbital
199 electronegativity of the chiral carbon atom (OEC^*) and surface tension (ST), among
200 others. Variables x_{26} to x_{55} correspond to molecular topological parameters predicted by
201 ChemAxon; for instance, aromatic ring count (Arc). In addition, from the molecular

202 descriptor logarithm of octanol–water partition coefficient ($\log P$, from ACD/Labs),
203 variable x_{56} , two additional variables (x_{57} and x_{58}), the apparent $\log P$ at a given pH ($\log D$)
204 and the molar total charge (α), were calculated in this work at pH 8 (the working pH),
205 using the following equations [22]:

$$\log \delta_i = \log \left(\frac{\beta_i h^i}{1 + \beta_1 h + \beta_2 h^2 + \dots + \beta_i h^i + \dots + \beta_n h^n} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\log D = \log P + \log \delta_i \quad (2)$$

$$\alpha = \sum_{j=0}^n a_j \delta_j \quad (3)$$

206 In these equations, δ_i is the molar fraction of the neutral form of the compound, h
207 is the proton concentration (i.e. $h = 10^{-8}$ M at pH 8.0), β_i is the protonation cumulative
208 constant (for a polyprotic system, $\beta_n = K_1 \cdot K_2 \cdot \dots \cdot K_i \cdot \dots \cdot K_n$), a_j is the value with its sign of
209 the net charge of the considered specie (i.e. -1, 0, +1, +2, ...) and δ_j the molar fraction of
210 the considered specie at the considered pH. The values of the logarithm of the protonation
211 constants ($\log K$) used to calculate the molar fractions were taken from the literature [23].

212 It should be noted that $\log D$ is available from ACD/Labs only at pH 5.5 and 7.4,
213 so we preferred to use eqs. 1 and 2 to perform the calculation at the experimental pH (8)
214 used to obtain the enantioresolution data. On the other hand, α (eqs. 1 and 3), non-
215 included in the above-mentioned papers [19, 20], was introduced for the first time in this
216 work as a potential predictor variable for enantioresolution.

217 Principal component analysis (PCA) and ~~discriminant partial least squares, for one~~
218 ~~response categorical variable~~ (DPLS1) models have been performed using The
219 Unscrambler® v.9.2 multivariate analysis software [24].

220 During DPLS1 model refinement (variable selection stage), the predictive power,
221 Pp , has been used as the optimization parameter to define the effective predictive ability
222 of the model. Pp was calculated using the following equation [25]:

$$Pp = 2EV_{CV} - EV \quad (4)$$

223 where EV is the explained variance and EV_{CV} its cross-validated value for the response
224 variable. A value of $Pp \geq 55\%$ has been considered acceptable for discriminant models
225 [19].

226

227 **3. Results and discussion**

228 *3.1. Experimental and categorised enantioresolution*

229 Table 1 shows the experimental enantioresolution data (R_s) obtained using the
230 screening procedure depicted in section 2.3 for the compounds studied (Table S1 in
231 supplementary data includes the 2D structure of the compounds). Compounds are
232 arranged according to their drug/pesticide families. In previous papers dealing with
233 enantioresolution modelling in EKC, the modelling of categorised (R_sC) instead of
234 experimental R_s values were recommended [19, 20]. The use of a categorical R_sC variable
235 to be modelled and predicted fits the main aim of the present paper, which is just to
236 anticipate whether a new compound will be enantioresolved or not in the chromatographic
237 conditions assayed. So, the experimental R_s values were converted into categorised R_sC
238 values (see Table 1). Compounds showing baseline enantioresolution (e.g. $R_s \gtrsim 1.7$; No
239 = 1, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 23 and 24 in Table 1) were assigned to $R_sC = 1$. The rest of compounds
240 were assigned to $R_sC = 0$, with the exception of propranolol (No 27; $R_s = 1.4$), for which

241 an $R_sC = 0.5$ was selected, taking into account that it is close to the baseline
242 enantioresolution in these conditions.

243

244 3.2. Structural influence (influential compounds)

245 The detection and elimination of influential compounds with dissimilar structure
246 is of utmost importance prior to developing any kind of model. These compounds could
247 disturb the internal structure of latent variables of the further DPLS1 model, so they
248 should be eliminated to avoid the alteration of structure-enantioresolution relationships.
249 In order to detect possible influential compounds, a PCA analysis was performed (~~see~~
250 ~~details in supplementary data~~). For this purpose, the structural information described in
251 section 2.4 were organised into a 34×58 \mathbf{X} -matrix. The options autoscaled data and leave-
252 one-out (LOO) cross-validation were chosen.

253 Figure 1A shows the PC1-PC2 bi-plot showing the scores (relationships between
254 compounds) and loadings (relationships between variables). As can be observed,
255 terfenadine and verapamil (*No* 22 and 33, respectively, in Table 1; whose scores are
256 indicated into the plot) have differential scores in the direction of a superimposed axis
257 (dashed line). This axis represents a large set of correlated variables related to the
258 molecular size (e.g. variables x_{18} , MSA and x_{23} , MM). For instance, the molecular mass
259 (MM) of the compounds *No* 22 and 33 are 471.70 and 454.60 Da, respectively. However,
260 the rest of compound have MM values in the 238.33 to 336.43 Da range. The molecular
261 surface area (MSA ; from Chem Axon) is another example of molecular dissimilarity.
262 Whereas MSA values of the compounds 22 and 33 are 780.90 and 797.90 Å²,
263 respectively, for the rest of compound are in the 374.70 to 579.98 Å² range. Thus, fixing

264 threshold limits for one or two of these variables could enable to identify new influential
265 compounds without the need to perform a new PCA analysis.

266

267 Figure 1B shows the Influence plot (Residual vs. Leverage) for compounds. It
268 confirms that both compounds are influential (high leverage), in agreement with the
269 results obtained in previous papers [19, 20]. Influential compounds (with different
270 structures from the majority) could disturb the structure-*RsC* relationship and should be
271 eliminated.

272

273 3.3. Modelling the structure-*RsC* relationship (DPLS1) and variable selection process

274 DPLS1 modelling was selected to relate the structural data (**X**-matrix) to the *RsC*
275 data (**y**-vector), as suggested in previous papers [19, 20]. To build the DPLS1 model, the
276 influential compounds *No* 22 and 33 were omitted. As in the PCA analysis, autoscaled
277 data and the LOO cross-validation options were used.

278 Several criteria were adopted to optimise the model. Ideally, the model should fit
279 the following goals: (i) A primary goal is to achieve full discrimination between the group
280 of compounds with predicted *RsC* = 0 and 1, for the calibration outputs (all compounds
281 in the model), and if possible, for the cross-validated outputs; (ii) The predictive power
282 *Pp* has to be $\geq 55\%$, (the recommended level [19]); (iii) The optimal number of latent
283 variables (k_o) has to be close to 1, for instance, $k_o = 1$ or 2 ($k_o = 1$, is the ideal value here
284 since there is just one response variable, *RsC*); (iv) The final model has to have significant
285 or almost significant variables (i.e. $\mathbf{b} \pm \mathbf{U}\mathbf{b}$ does not include zero).

286 The initial DPLS1 model derived provided full discrimination between
287 compounds having $RsC = 0$ and 1 in the calibration set (see Fig. S1 in supplementary
288 data). Therefore, this initial model fits the primary goal of this work. However, some
289 compounds were misclassified in the cross-validated outputs (mainly *No* 1 and 23,
290 validation plot in Fig. S1). In addition, other negative aspects were also observed. A poor
291 predictive power was obtained, $Pp = 0$, due to an excessive distance between EV and
292 EV_{CV} , 78.3% and 30.6%, respectively. This fact also justifies the differences in the
293 prediction success rates between the calibration and cross-validated outputs. On the other
294 hand, a value of $k_0 = 4$ was obtained (far from the ideal one), indicating an excessive
295 model complexity. Finally, the scaled regression coefficients indicate that practically all
296 the variables were non-significant, with the exception of x_4 (C^*hA), x_{57} ($\log D$) and x_{58}
297 (α). These three variables will probably remain in the final model, but most of the rest
298 would contribute negatively to the poor predictive ability of the current model.

299 Model refinement (e.g. elimination of noisy variables, that is, those with the worst
300 Ub/b ratios) has proven to be convenient in order to improve its performance. Also Pp
301 has been proposed to control the progress of refinement instead of other more common
302 parameters as EV or EV_{CV} [19 and references therein]. In the present study, the process
303 of model refinement was performed in two stages, due to the high number of variables.
304 In addition, the Pp value was used as an indicator to control the quality of the model.

305 In the first refinement stage, the elimination of noisy variables was carried out in
306 turn in several steps, deleting up to 4 variables at each step. The process was stopped
307 when the remaining variables in the model showed comparable importance (comparable
308 $b \pm Ub$ values). In this case, model refinement was stopped for 15 remaining variables.
309 Figure 2 shows the evolution of the parameters k_0 and EV , EV_{CV} and Pp while decreasing

310 the number of variables into the model during this refinement stage. As can be expected,
311 the values of Pp raise and k_o decrease along the process, indicating an improvement in
312 the quality of the model.

313 On the other hand, as can be seen in Figure 2, the use of EV (related with the
314 calibration set) to control the refinement progress is not adequate in this case. The model
315 refinement from 35 to 31 remaining variables resulted in a decrease in the EV values, due
316 to the change from $k_o = 4$ to $k_o = 2$. This decrease in the EV values suggests an apparent
317 loss of predictive ability that would lead to incorrectly stopping the refinement process.
318 EV_{CV} seems to be a better diagnostic indicator. However, from 31 to 24 remaining
319 variables (with $k_o = 2$), there is a stabilization of the parameter (even a little decrease) that
320 would incorrectly suggest no further improvement, as in the case of EV . Therefore, Pp
321 (relating both calibration and cross-validated outputs) is the best option to measure the
322 improvement of the DPLS1 model. Pp also exhibits a higher relative slope (improvement)
323 than EV_{CV} . To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that the superiority of Pp
324 to control model refinement, compared with other more conventional criteria, is outlined.
325 In fact, a high Pp value guaranties a short distance between calibration and cross-
326 validated predictions (i.e. the model robustness) and, as a consequence, can assure the
327 achievement of the primary goal mentioned above.

328 In the second refinement stage, the elimination of variables was performed one by
329 one, eliminating each time that one whose elimination greatly improved Pp , without
330 affecting negatively the others consolidated rules. This stage was stopped when the
331 elimination of any new variable worsen the quality of the model (Pp or any other feature).
332 Some technical details of the final model can be seen in supplementary data (Fig S2).
333 Only nine variables, with acceptable $\mathbf{b} \pm \mathbf{Ub}$ values, remained in the final model: two

334 chiral-topological parameters, x_1 and x_4 (C^*X and C^*hA , respectively), a molecular
335 topological parameter, x_{36} (Arc) and six molecular descriptors, x_{11} , x_{18} , x_{21} , x_{25} , x_{57} and x_{58}
336 ($zmin$, MSA , OEC^* , ST , $\log D$ and α , respectively).

337 The model exhibited good discrimination between predicted $RsC = 0$ and 1 data
338 for calibration, and cross-validated outputs. It exhibited, a Pp value of 56% ($EV = 78.4\%$
339 and $EV_{CV} = 67.4\%$), with $k_o = 2$, near to the ideal value. So, the model was considered
340 satisfactory for the purpose of this work. The values of the variables included in the final
341 model for the compounds studied are shown in Table 2.

342

343 3.4. RsC -variables relationships

344 The magnitude of the scaled regression coefficients (**b**-magnitude) reflects the
345 importance of each selected variable to describe the enantioresolution. Positive **b**-values
346 indicate positive contributions (i.e. a high value of the variable favours the
347 enantioresolution) and vice versa. According to this, α (negative contribution) is the
348 variable that contributes the most to enantioresolution since its coefficient doubles the
349 importance over the other variables (see Fig S2 in supplementary data). Therefore, neutral
350 and low charged compounds (α close to zero) have a priori the largest probability of
351 enantioresolution.

352 The other eight variables of the model have similar importance between them
353 (similar coefficient magnitudes). This fact indicates that their contribution to the
354 enantioresolution is almost equivalent. The absence of heteroatoms or aromatic
355 heterocycles (C^*X and C^*hA ; negative coefficients) directly linked to the chiral carbon
356 (C^*), as well as the presence of the aromatic rings in the molecule (aromatic ring count
357 (Arc); positive contribution), also improve the enantioresolution. In the same way, low

358 *zmin* and *MSA* values and high *OEC**, *ST* and *logD* values enhance the enantioresolution.
359 It should be noted that *logD* but not *logP* was selected to obtain the final model. Thus, for
360 ionisable compounds, the effective hydrophobicity, adjusted with the mobile phase pH,
361 could contribute to improve the enantioresolution.

362 As stated in the introduction section, the results obtained confirm that
363 hydrophobic, electronic and steric factors are the main interactions responsible of
364 enantioresolution in polysaccharide-based stationary phases.

365 As can be seen in Table 2, seven of the enantioresolved compounds (*No* = 5, 6, 7,
366 8, 9, 23 and 24) have low α values (in the 0 – 0.33 range), while the majority of the non-
367 enantioresolved compounds have $\alpha > 0.92$. This behaviour is in agreement with that
368 previously stated. However, for some compounds the contribution of the rest of variables
369 becomes more important than the effect of α . For example, although nomifensine (*No* 1)
370 has a relatively high α value (0.88; unfavourable for *RsC*), it is enantioresolved due to the
371 combination of other favourable parameters (e.g. it has the lowest *MSA* value, 374.7 Å²).
372 On the contrary, enantioresolution was not achieved for metalaxyl (*No* 10) despite being
373 a neutral compound ($\alpha = 0$; favourable for *RsC*). This molecule has, for instance, one *C*X*
374 (the *C*-N* bond) and just one aromatic ring (*Arc* = 1), among other non-favourable
375 contributions (see Table 1).

376 Figure 3 shows the final DPLS1 score plot. Scores are labelled by their compound
377 numbers (*No* in Table 1; Figure 3A), *RsC* values (Figure 3B, upper part) and their families
378 (Figure 3C, lower part). As can be seen, compounds having *RsC* = 1 are located in the
379 right space, which is logical attending the *RsC* position in the loading plot (Fig. S2 in
380 supplementary data). These points correspond to the family 2 (fungicides, except
381 metalaxyl, *No* 10) and to two local anaesthetics and one antidepressant (families 4 and 1,

382 respectively). In the central part of the score plot, several families are mixed, all of them
383 with $R_sC = 0$. β -blockers (family 5, $R_sC = 0$) are located in the left upper quadrant, except
384 propranolol (*No 27*), the only compound close to the baseline enantioresolution ($R_sC =$
385 0.5). Thus, the DPLS1 results are discreetly conditioned by the families of the compounds
386 studied.

387

388 3.5. *Explicit model for enantioresolution anticipation*

389 In order to easily anticipate whether or not a new compound will be
390 enantioresolved, a practical explicit model was derived from DPLS1. For this purpose,
391 raw (de-scaled) coefficients were calculated from the scaled ones. The following equation
392 was obtained (eq. 5):

$$393 \quad eRs = -1.28 - 0.14 C^*X - 0.22 C^*hA - 0.078 zmin - 0.0022 MSA + 0.25 OEC^* + \\ 394 \quad 0.024 ST + 0.22 Arc + 0.072 \log D - 0.57 \alpha \quad (5)$$

395 where eRs refers to an output related to R_s that should be seen as an indicative value since
396 categorical R_s data were used to obtain the model. Figure 4 shows the eRs outputs
397 obtained from eq. 5 vs the initial assigned R_sC values (Table 1) for the compounds of the
398 calibration set.

399 To anticipate enantioresolution, eRs outputs have to be transformed into
400 anticipated- R_sC ($aRsC$) outputs, comparable to the categorical (R_sC) levels previously
401 established. For this purpose, as Figure 4 shows, it is necessary to apply the following
402 rules: (i) $aRsC = 1$, full enantioresolution, for $eRs > 0.5$; (ii) $aRsC = 0.5$, almost full
403 enantioresolution, for eRs between 0.4 and 0.5 and (iii) $aRsC = 0$, poor or no
404 enantioresolution, for $eRs < 0.4$.

405 Alternatively, a simpler approach can be applied to establish if a molecule will be
406 completely enantioresolved ($aRsC = 1$) or not ($aRsC = 0$). In this case, $aRsC$ levels (0 or
407 1) are calculated by directly rounding the eRs values to integer numbers (without decimal
408 digits). Table 2 shows the $aRsC$ values obtained by applying this direct rule. Such
409 anticipations are identical to those obtained by applying the previous rules, except for
410 propranolol ($RsC = 0.5$) as expected. For this compound, this approach anticipates no full
411 enantioresolution ($aRsC = 0$), which strictly agrees with the experimental result, $Rs = 1.4$.
412 An anticipation success rate of 100% was obtained by comparing $aRsC$ (Table 2) and RsC
413 assignments from experimental data (Table 1).

414

415 3.6. Protocol for a safe $aRsC$ anticipation and additional remarks

416 A complete protocol to perform a safe $aRsC$ anticipation for a new compound in
417 the current conditions is:

- 418 • Step-1a. Obtain MSA from ChemAxon (this value will be necessary in further steps).
419 Optionally, obtain the molecular mass (MM).
- 420 • Step-1b. If MSA is outside the 350 – 600 Å² range the anticipation is not
421 recommended (for more security, anticipation should not be done if MM is outside
422 the 200 - 350 Da range). Otherwise, continue to the next steps.
- 423 • Step-2a. Locate the chiral carbon (C^*) in the 2D structure of the chiral compound.
424 Find the presence or absence of C^* -heteroatoms (C^*X) and C^* -aromatic heterocycles
425 (C^*hA) bonds. Assign a value to these parameters according to the criteria: C^*X
426 presence (1); C^*X absence (0); C^*hA presence (1); C^*hA absence (0). Count the
427 aromatic rings in the whole molecule (Arc is also provided by ChemAxon).

- 428 • Step-2b. Use ChemAxon to calculate the values of the variables $zmin$, MSA , OEC^* ,
429 ST and pKa . From ACD/LogP estimate $\log P$.
- 430 • Step-2c. Calculate $\log D$ and α at pH 8, according to eqs. 1-3.
- 431 • Step-3. Use eq. 5 to estimate eRs . Round this value to an integer number for a rapid
432 anticipation of enantioresolution, ($aRsC$ only 0 or 1). Alternatively, use the following
433 criteria for a 3-level $aRsC$: baseline enantioresolution ($aRsC = 1$) if $eRs > 0.5$, poor
434 or non enantioresolution ($aRsC = 0$) if $eRs < 0.4$, and almost full enantioresolution
435 ($aRsC = 0.5$) if eRs is in the 0.4 – 0.5 range.

436

437 [abajo?] The compounds included in this study are structurally unrelated (drugs
438 and pesticides) compounds. Except fungicides (compounds *No* 5-10), which are neutral,
439 all are basic compounds, most of them fully ionised at pH = 8.0. *A priori*, the anticipation
440 protocol should be applicable for compounds of similar nature, in experimental conditions
441 similar to those used in this study (section 2.3).

442 The LOO cross-validation strategy performed on the final DPLS1 model is
443 virtually equivalent to the use of an external validation strategy [25]. Note that in this
444 approach, the prediction, in turn, of each single compound (acting at that moment as an
445 external validation sample), is made with a model very close to the final model (just
446 excluding the compound to be predicted).

447 On the other hand, to test the anticipative ability of the protocol with compounds
448 (not included to build the model), four molecules satisfying the step-1b of the protocol
449 were first anticipated applying the protocol and then chromatographed for experimental
450 confirmation. Three of them provided $eRs < 0.4$ (Step 3 of the protocol), thus, they were
451 anticipated as non-resolved ($aRsC = 0$). Their parameters (listed between brackets in the
452 order indicated in Table 2) were: fenfluramine (1, 0, 8.79, 359.91, 8.05, 26.3, 1, 0.83,

453 0.99); amlodipine (0, 0, 11.71, 570.9, 8.42, 44.4, 1, 2.71, 0.96) and bupivacaine (1, 0,
454 8.21, 517.09, 8.82, 41.6, 1, 3.3, 0.5). In the three cases, experimental enantioresolution
455 values ($R_s = 0, 0.6$ and 0.8 , respectively), confirmed the anticipation.

456 The fourth compound was bicalutamide, whose parameters (1, 0, 6.99, 527.46,
457 9.44, 58.2, 2, 4.94, 0) provided $eR_s > 0.5$, thus, it was anticipated as enantioresolved
458 ($aR_sC = 1$). Its experimental $R_s = 1.7$ confirmed, again, the anticipation.

459

460 **4. Conclusions**

461 Structural information of structurally unrelated chiral compounds can be
462 connected with experimental enantioresolution data in HPLC obtained using immobilised
463 cellulose tris(3,5-dichlorophenylcarbamate) column in reversed phase conditions. Safe
464 anticipation of the categorised (i.e. favourable/unfavourable) enantioresolution is
465 possible. It requires a precise discriminant PLS-based (DPLS1) multivariate study; i.e.
466 combining scaled regression coefficients and their uncertainty intervals with the
467 predictive power (Pp) values for a consistent model refinement. Such study provides
468 double valuable information: (i) the variables more informative and their contribution
469 (positive or negative) to the enantioresolution of a compound (descriptive function), and
470 (ii) an explicit equation to anticipate its enantioresolution (predictive function).

471 From 58 initial structural variables, three topological parameters (two of them
472 connected to the chiral carbon), and six molecular descriptors (one of them also related
473 with the chiral carbon), are selected after a discriminant partial least squares refinement
474 process. The topology surrounding the chiral carbon is a relevant aspect on
475 enantioresolution. However, in this case, the molar total charge, which depends on the
476 mobile phase pH (α), becomes the most important descriptor. Accordingly, the

477 enantioresolution of neutral or low charged basic compounds is favoured. On the other
478 hand, the model discriminates between two of the families studied, fungicides and β -
479 blockers.

480 A stepwise protocol facilitates the anticipation of the enantioresolution without
481 the need of the previous derived models. It includes threshold limits, based on the
482 topological parameter aromatic ring count, to detect influential compounds whose
483 anticipation becomes risky. Applying the protocol, an anticipation success rate of 100%
484 for the compounds studied is obtained, when compared with the experimental results. The
485 high *R_s*-anticipation effectiveness found suggests that the strategy could serve for other
486 RPLC or in general HPLC chiral methods.

487 On the other hand, it should be taken into account that the current results
488 correspond to a concrete column...

489

490

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571

572 **Figure captions**

573 Fig. 1. Unscrambler® PCA results. (A) PC1-PC2 bi-plot showing the scores
574 (relationships between compounds; +) and loadings (relationships between variables; ○).
575 (B) Influence plot (Residual vs. Leverage) for compounds.

576

577 Fig. 2. DPLS1 outputs as a function of the number of remaining variables in the model
578 during the first stage of the refinement process. Explained (EV , ×) and cross-validated
579 (EV_{CV} , +) variance values for the response variable, predictive power (Pp , ○) and optimal
580 number of latent variables (k_o , —).

581

582 Fig. 3. Final (refined) DPLS1 score plot labelled using variables in Table 1. Compounds
583 are labelled by their number (No), categorical enantioresolution (RsC) and their
584 drug/pesticide family. See further details in Table 1.

585

586 Fig. 4. Enantioresolution discriminant ability of eq. 5. Estimates from eq. 5 (eRs outputs)
587 vs. RsC values from Table 1. Horizontal lines at 0.4 and 0.5 separate the three initial RsC
588 levels (0, 0.5 and 1).

589